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Competencies In Scientific Literacy Of Pre-Service Versus In-Service Chemistry Teachers In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy in Taraba State, Nigeria; aimed to provide insights into improving these competencies, which are crucial for effective instruction and fostering scientific literacy among students in the region. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 851 from which 358 were pre-service chemistry teachers and 493 were in-service chemistry teachers. Krejcie and Morgan table was used to select a total sample size of 403 with 186 pre-service teachers and 217 in-service teachers. Stratified proportionate and simple random samplings were used as sampling techniques. The data collection tool was Test of Scientific Literacy (TOSL) with 9 levels of scientific literacy adapted from Gormally et al. (2012). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts; and pilot tested with a reliability index of 0.80 through KR-20. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that overall; in-service chemistry teachers have significantly higher scientific literacy than pre-service chemistry teachers ($p < 0.05$). Pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy does not statistically differ based on gender ($p > 0.05$). The study concluded that the current teachers of chemistry in Taraba State have better scientific literacy than the prospective teachers of chemistry and recommended that pre-service chemistry teachers' curriculum and training processes should be reviewed and emphasis be made on the acquisition of scientific literacy.

Keywords: Science literacy, Chemistry teachers, Competencies, Pre-service, In-service, Gender

INTRODUCTION

Science education is credited for the scientific and technological development of nations around the world. Science education involves teaching students about scientific concepts, methods, and processes to foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. It spans various disciplines like biology, chemistry, and physics among others. Science education enables individuals to understand and evaluate scientific information in everyday life. Effective science education also equips students with the ability to analyse data, question assumptions, and apply evidence-based reasoning to real-world problems. In other words, it improves the scientific literacy of individuals making them useful to themselves and their societies.

Lemmon et al. (2023) defined scientific literacy as the ability to understand, interpret, and apply scientific concepts, processes, and reasoning to make informed decisions in everyday life. It involves not only knowledge of scientific facts but also an understanding of the scientific method, critical thinking, and the ability to evaluate evidence-based claims. For chemistry teachers, scientific literacy is essential because it enables them to effectively communicate complex chemical concepts in an accessible way, fostering student understanding and engagement. It equips teachers to address misconceptions, connect chemistry to real-world applications, and inspire curiosity about the subject. Budiman et al. (2021) alluded that scientifically literate teachers can also model critical thinking and evidence-based reasoning, helping students develop these skills. Ultimately, their literacy ensures they

can adapt to new scientific developments and teach students to navigate a world increasingly shaped by science and technology. Teachers of chemistry, in particular, must be scientifically literate. This is because the scientific literacy of students presently and the future generation depends on the teachers. In other words, students' low or high scientific literacy depends on the teachers (Rubini et al., 2018). A scientifically literate chemistry teacher can connect classroom topics, such as the properties of acids and bases, to current events like environmental issues such as acid rain or personal decisions (such as understanding the pH levels in household products). This makes the subject matter more relevant and engaging for students, demonstrating that chemistry is not just an academic discipline but a tool for navigating the world. Teachers could empower students to become responsible citizens who can make sense of the chemical world around them, from understanding product labels to evaluating debates on environmental policy.

In the context of this study where investigation of scientific literacy was conducted, teachers of chemistry were considered along two lines: the pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers. Owusu-Ansah (2017) posited that assessing the competencies of pre-service and in-service teachers in the teaching and learning of chemistry is an essential step toward ensuring the quality of science education in a country. An in-service teacher could be described as a qualified and certified teacher who is currently plying his trade in the classroom. Consequently, an in-service chemistry teacher would be considered as a trained, certified and employed educational personnel saddled with the responsibility of implementing chemistry curriculum especially at the secondary level of education.

In-service teachers are vital to education as they actively deliver instruction, shaping students' academic and personal growth. Exploration of in-service chemistry teachers' scientific literacy is important for a number of reasons. First, in today's digital age, students are constantly exposed to a flood of information, including unproven claims and pseudoscience; scientific literacy equips teachers to critically evaluate information and to teach students how to distinguish between credible scientific evidence and misinformation. A chemistry teacher with strong scientific literacy can help students analyse a viral social media post about a "miracle cure" or a news report on a new energy source, prompting them to ask questions about the source, methodology, and evidence. This skill is crucial for fostering an informed citizenry. Second, students' learning achievement depends on the quality of the teachers. In Taraba State, data from the State's Ministry of Education reveals that from 2016 to 2023, less than 50% of secondary school students who sat for external examinations passed chemistry with at least credit grade. This could infer low scientific literacy on the part of the students which also could translate into low scientific literacy of the in-service chemistry teachers. Alternatively, the in-service teachers are out-dated or not in tune with current realities where innovative classroom practices such as ones that require technology are used for chemistry instruction. Studies conducted to determine in-service teachers' scientific literacy and related concepts have produced different results. For instance, Najah et al. (2023) observed that professionally trained chemistry teachers exhibited higher knowledge of teaching and assessment in chemistry than the untrained chemistry teachers. However, Clores and Reganit (2020) observed that in-service teachers have medium level literacy in assessment as opposed to high level that in-service teachers ought to have. In view of this, prospective chemistry teachers who are currently undergoing training in various teacher training institutions ought to be trained along these lines so that they could effectively enhance students' scientific literacy and solve low achievement problems in chemistry when they are employed to teach chemistry.

A pre-service teacher, also called prospective teacher is a student undergoing educational training to become a teacher. A pre-service chemistry teacher is a student currently being trained to teach chemistry in schools. University students enrolled into the programme of education and chemistry (chemistry education) belong to this category. Current realities demand these set of students acquire the necessary skills and requisite knowledge to impact conceptual understanding and meaningful delivery of lesson of primary school and secondary school students. As regards science or chemistry pre-service or in-service teachers' competencies, previous studies assessed in hybrid pre-service teachers' enrolment and achievement (Jack, 2020) and effective utilization of ICT resources (Jack, 2021) and in-service teachers on utilization or competencies on ICT resources (Jack & Ayuba, 2021; Jack & Barau, 2021), but there exist serious literature gaps on teachers, competencies in science literacy mostly blended teacher status (pre-service and in-service) and in the subject area (chemistry) which this present study fitted in.

The scientific literacy of prospective chemistry teachers is crucial because they are the primary conduits for fostering this same skill in their future students. Without a strong foundation in scientific literacy themselves, teachers cannot effectively model the process of scientific inquiry, which goes beyond rote memorization of facts. Studies conducted on pre-service teachers' scientific literacy have yielded varying results. Sarini et al. (2024) found that literacy achievement of prospective science teachers is very low with respect to scientific literacy. Similarly, Irwanto et al. (2018) reported that pre-service chemistry teachers' critical thinking skills are at low level. Contrasting report was presented by Obodo et al. (2024) who reported high scientific literacy of pre-service teachers in Enugu State University of Science and Technology. Beyond abilities and literacy level, several other socio-demographic factors could influence both pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy.

Pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy could be influenced by gender. Historically, the field of chemistry (and science in general) has seen a lower representation of women, both in terms of professional scientists and educators (Ezeh, 2016). Gambari et al. (2017) asserted that this imbalance can impact students' perceptions of who belongs in the field and who is capable of succeeding in it. Among in-service teachers, Akili and Kuturu (2022) found that there is no significant gender difference in scientific literacy of in-service teachers. Malabo (2024) found that assessment literacy levels did not significantly differ by gender of basic education teachers. Alternatively, Ihenetu-Hyginus and Wali (2022) reported that female teachers' assessment literacy level is significantly higher than the male teachers.

Among pre-service teachers, varying reports have been documented related to scientific literacy differences based on gender. Cavas (2015) reported that pre-service teachers' level of scientific literacy is regardless of their gender. Agbenyeku and Arowolo (2024) observed no significant difference in the scores of male and female pre-service science teachers with reference to scientific literacy. Kristiyasari et al. (2018) found that university students' literacy skills are influenced by gender differences. Aina et al. (2020) showed male pre-service teachers possessed more scientific literacy skills than their female counterparts. Promoting female chemistry educators both in the curriculum and through role modelling can help combat these biases.

The study aimed to compare pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' scientific literacy, considering gender in Taraba State to understand the localized context of teacher competency for a better science education. Specifically, the study compared the science literacy skills of: i. Pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers; ii. Male and female pre-service chemistry teachers; and, iii. Male and female in-service chemistry teachers in Taraba State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the mean scientific literacy score of pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?
- ii. What is the mean scientific literacy score of male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?
- iii. What is the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive-comparative survey research design was adopted for the study. The design was appropriate for the current study as the study sought to assess pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' scientific literacy without inferring a cause-and-effect relationship to the observations. The study was conducted in Taraba State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 851 which comprised

all pre-service chemistry teachers in Federal University Wukari and Taraba State University Jalingo and all the in-service chemistry teachers across the 12 education zones all the secondary schools in Taraba State, Nigeria in the 2024/2025 academic session. From this number (851), 359 were pre-service chemistry teachers and 493 were in-service chemistry teachers. The sample size of 403 was used in the study. Using Krejcie and Morgan table of population and sample distribution, sample sizes of 186 and 217 were obtained for pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers respectively. Stratified proportionate and simple random sampling techniques were used as sampling techniques. The pre-service teachers were stratified proportionately along institutions while the in-service teachers were stratified proportionately along education zones. This was to achieve equal representation of subjects. Simple random sampling was used to provide equal selection opportunities for members of the population.

Test of Scientific Literacy (TOSL) was used for data collection. TOSL is a 28-item multiple choice tests adapted from Gormally et al. (2012). TOSL has nine (9) different levels of Scientific Literacy (SL). SL1 involves three (3) items that test the literacy of identifying a valid scientific argument (which involves recognizing when scientific evidence supports a hypothesis); SL2 involves five (5) items that test the literacy of conducting an effective literature search (e.g. evaluate the validity of sources (e.g., websites, peer reviewed journals) and distinguish between types of sources); SL3 involves three (3) items that test the literacy of evaluating the use and misuse of scientific information (e.g. recognize a valid scientific course of action, distinguish the appropriate use of science to make societal decisions); SL4 involves four (4) items that test the literacy of comprehension of elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions (e.g. identify strengths and weaknesses in research related to bias, sample size, randomization, experimental control); SL5 involves one (1) item on making a graph i.e. graphical representations of data; SL6 involves four (4) items that test the literacy of read and interpreting graphical representations of data; SL7 involves three (3) items on solving problems using quantitative skills, including probability and statistics (e.g. calculate means, probabilities, percentages, frequencies); SL8 involves three (3) items that test the understanding and interpretation of basic statistics (e.g. interpret error bars, understand the need for statistics); and SL9 involves two (2) items that test justifying inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data.

The instrument was face and content validated by three experts: two from the Department of Science Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Educational foundations. All of whom were from Faculty of Education, Taraba State University, Jalingo. Kuder Richardson 20 reliability index of 0.80 was obtained for TOSL after a pilot test conducted with 35 respondents in Adamawa State. The descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer all the research questions while the inferential statistics of independent t-test were used to test all the null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance

RESULTS

The results from the data analyzed are presented and interpreted with the 9 Science Literacy (SL) represented as SL1-SL9 (SL1. Identify a valid scientific argument, SL2. Conduct an effective literature search, SL3. Evaluate the use and misuse of scientific information, SL4. Understand elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions, SL5. Make a graphical representations of data, SL6. Read and interpret graphical representations of data, SL7. Solve problems using quantitative skills, including probability and statistics, SL8. Understand and interpret basic statistics, and SL9. Justify inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data).

Research Question One: *What is the mean scientific literacy score of pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-service and In-service Chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy

Scientific Literacy	Teacher	N	Mean	Std dev	Diff.
SL1	Pre-service	186	1.22	0.65	0.15
	In-service	217	1.37	0.72	
SL2	Pre-service	186	1.17	1.08	0.39
	In-service	217	1.56	1.24	
SL3	Pre-service	186	1.29	0.79	0.30
	In-service	217	1.59	0.94	
SL4	Pre-service	186	0.90	0.93	0.36
	In-service	217	1.26	0.90	
SL5	Pre-service	186	0.18	0.38	0.10
	In-service	217	0.28	0.45	
SL6	Pre-service	186	1.06	0.79	0.20
	In-service	217	1.26	0.85	
SL7	Pre-service	186	1.11	0.74	0.19
	In-service	217	1.30	0.80	
SL8	Pre-service	186	1.17	0.65	0.12
	In-service	217	1.29	0.70	
SL9	Pre-service	186	0.83	0.67	0.09
	In-service	217	0.92	0.82	
Overall SL	Pre-service	186	8.94	5.74	1.90
	In-service	217	10.84	6.30	

Table 1 shows the results of test of scientific literacy between pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers. The table shows the 9 levels of Scientific Literacy (9) in this study. It could be seen that in-service chemistry teachers performed better than pre-service teachers in each of the 9 levels of SL. Overall, from the table, pre-service chemistry teachers have a mean SL score of 8.94 with standard deviation of 5.74 whereas in-service chemistry teachers have a mean score of 10.84 with standard deviation of 6.30. The mean SL scores show that in-service chemistry teachers have higher scientific literacy score than pre-service chemistry teachers. The standard deviation values show that there is a greater spread or variation of scores among in-service teachers compared to the pre-service chemistry teachers.

Research Question 2: *What is the mean scientific literacy score of male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-service Chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy based on Gender

Scientific Literacy	Gender	N	Mean	Std dev	Diff
SL1	Male	68	1.15	0.61	0.11
	Female	118	1.26	0.67	
SL2	Male	68	1.06	1.09	0.18
	Female	118	1.24	1.08	
SL3	Male	68	1.24	0.65	0.08
	Female	118	1.32	0.87	
SL4	Male	68	0.94	0.94	0.07
	Female	118	0.87	0.93	
SL5	Male	68	0.13	0.34	0.07
	Female	118	0.20	0.40	
SL6	Male	68	1.10	0.74	0.07
	Female	118	1.03	0.83	
SL7	Male	68	1.12	0.70	0.02
	Female	118	1.10	0.76	
SL8	Male	68	1.18	0.73	0.01
	Female	118	1.17	0.60	
SL9	Male	68	0.79	0.64	0.07
	Female	118	0.86	0.68	
Overall SL	Male	68	8.71	5.46	0.36
	Female	118	9.07	5.91	

Table 2 shows the results of test of scientific literacy between male and female pre-service chemistry teachers. Male pre-service chemistry teachers outperformed their female counterparts in SL4, SL6, SL7 and SL8; while the female pre-service chemistry teachers scored higher than their male counterparts in SL1, SL2, SL3, SL5, and SL9. This means that the male pre-service teachers showed higher literacy than their female counterparts in understanding elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions; reading and interpreting graphical representations of data; solving problems using quantitative skills, including probability and statistics; and understanding and interpreting basic statistics. On the other hand, the female pre-service teachers showed higher literacy than their male counterparts in terms of identifying a valid scientific argument; conducting an effective literature search; evaluating the use and misuse of scientific information; making a graph; and justifying inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data.

From Table 2, the overall mean values for scientific literacy showed that male pre-service chemistry teachers have a mean score of 8.71 with standard deviation of 5.46 whereas female pre-service teachers have a mean score of 9.07 with standard deviation of 5.91. The mean scores show that female pre-service chemistry teachers have higher overall scientific literacy score than male pre-service chemistry teachers with difference of 0.36. The standard deviation values show that there is a greater spread or variation of scores among the female pre-service chemistry teachers compared to the male pre-service chemistry teachers.

Research Question 3: *What is the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of In-service Chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy based on Gender

Scientific Literacy	Gender	N	Mean	Std dev	Diff
SL1	Male	132	1.38	0.74	0.02
	Female	85	1.36	0.71	
SL2	Male	132	1.50	1.24	0.16
	Female	85	1.66	1.23	
SL3	Male	132	1.48	0.95	0.27
	Female	85	1.75	0.90	
SL4	Male	132	1.23	0.96	0.06
	Female	85	1.29	0.81	
SL5	Male	132	0.29	0.45	0.03
	Female	85	0.26	0.44	
SL6	Male	132	1.20	0.98	0.15
	Female	85	1.35	0.59	
SL7	Male	132	1.23	0.82	0.19
	Female	85	1.42	0.76	
SL8	Male	132	1.39	0.72	0.24
	Female	85	1.15	0.65	
SL9	Male	132	0.88	0.83	0.11
	Female	85	0.99	0.79	
Overall SL	Male	132	10.58	6.61	0.66
	Female	85	11.24	5.80	

Table 3 shows the results of test of scientific literacy between male and female in-service chemistry teachers. Male in-service chemistry teachers outperformed their female counterparts in SL1, SL5 and SL8; this means that the male in-service have higher scientific literacy in terms of identifying a valid scientific argument, making a graph and Understand and interpret basic statistics respectively. The female in-service chemistry teachers showed higher literacy than their male counterparts in SL2, SL3, SL4, SL6, SL7, and SL9; this means that the female teachers are better than the male teachers in terms of conducting an effective literature search; evaluating the use and misuse of scientific information; understanding elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions; solving problems using quantitative skills; including probability and statistics; and justifying inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data.

From the table, overall, male in-service chemistry teachers have a mean SL score of 10.58 with standard deviation of 6.61 whereas female in-service chemistry teachers have a mean score of 11.24 with standard deviation of 5.80. The mean scores show that female in-service chemistry teachers have higher scientific literacy score than male in-service chemistry teachers with difference of 0.66. The standard deviation values show that there is a greater spread or variation of scores among the male in-service chemistry teachers compared to the female in-service chemistry teachers.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

Table 4: Independent t-test Result of Pre-service and In-service Chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy

Scientific Literacy	Teacher	N	Mean	Std dev	T	df	sig.
SL1	Pre-service	186	1.22	0.65	-2.22	401	0.027
	In-service	217	1.37	0.72			
SL2	Pre-service	186	1.17	1.08	-3.35	401	0.001
	In-service	217	1.56	1.24			
SL3	Pre-service	186	1.29	0.79	-3.43	401	0.001
	In-service	217	1.59	0.94			
SL4	Pre-service	186	0.90	0.93	-3.94	401	0.000
	In-service	217	1.26	0.90			
SL5	Pre-service	186	0.18	0.38	-2.36	401	0.019
	In-service	217	0.28	0.45			
SL6	Pre-service	186	1.06	0.79	-2.47	401	0.014
	In-service	217	1.26	0.85			
SL7	Pre-service	186	1.11	0.74	-2.56	401	0.011
	In-service	217	1.30	0.80			
SL8	Pre-service	186	1.17	0.65	-1.82	401	0.070
	In-service	217	1.29	0.70			
SL9	Pre-service	186	0.83	0.67	-1.18	401	0.239
	In-service	217	0.92	0.82			
Overall SL	Pre-service	186	8.94	5.74	-3.15	401	0.002
	In-service	217	10.84	6.30			

Table 4 shows the independent t-test result of the comparison between pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy. The table reveals that there is a significant difference between pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers in SL1, SL2, SL3, SL4, SL5, SL6, and SL7 ($p < 0.05$). However, there is no significant difference between the two groups of teachers in SL8 and SL9. In terms of overall scientific literacy comparison, t value of -3.15 was obtained and the degree of freedom is 401; the significance value is 0.002 which is less than the benchmark 0.05. This means that overall; there is a significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers. Consequently, null hypothesis 1 is rejected.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

Table 5: Independent t-test Result of Pre-service Teachers' Scientific Literacy based on Gender

Scientific Literacy	Gender	N	Mean	Std dev	T	df	sig.
SL1	Male	68	1.15	0.61	-1.17	184	0.243
	Female	118	1.26	0.67			
SL2	Male	68	1.06	1.09	-1.08	184	0.280
	Female	118	1.24	1.08			
SL3	Male	68	1.24	0.65	-0.72	184	0.474
	Female	118	1.32	0.87			
SL4	Male	68	0.94	0.94	0.48	184	0.632
	Female	118	0.87	0.93			
SL5	Male	68	0.13	0.34	-1.22	184	0.224
	Female	118	0.20	0.40			
SL6	Male	68	1.10	0.74	0.57	184	0.569
	Female	118	1.03	0.83			
SL7	Male	68	1.12	0.70	0.14	184	0.887
	Female	118	1.10	0.76			

SL8	Male	68	1.18	0.73	0.07	184	0.944
	Female	118	1.17	0.60			
SL9	Male	68	0.79	0.64	-0.61	184	0.543
	Female	118	0.86	0.68			
Overall SL	Male	68	8.71	5.46	-0.41	184	0.680
	Female	118	9.07	5.91			

Table 5 shows the independent t-test result of the comparison between male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy. The table reveals that in each of the 9 levels of scientific literacy (SL1 to SL9), the significance value was more than the benchmark 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). In terms of overall scientific literacy comparison by gender, a t value of -0.41 was obtained at degree of freedom of 184. The significance value is 0.680 which is greater than the benchmark 0.05. This means that overall; there is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female pre-service chemistry teachers. Consequently, null hypothesis 2 is not rejected but accepted.

Testing Null Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers' in Taraba State.

Table 6: Independent t-test Result of In-service Teachers' Scientific Literacy based on Gender

Scientific Literacy	Gender	N	Mean	Std dev	T	df	sig.
SL1	Male	132	1.38	0.74	0.14	215	0.889
	Female	85	1.36	0.71			
SL2	Male	132	1.50	1.24	-0.92	215	0.356
	Female	85	1.66	1.23			
SL3	Male	132	1.48	0.95	-2.07	215	0.040
	Female	85	1.75	0.90			
SL4	Male	132	1.23	0.96	-0.47	215	0.637
	Female	85	1.29	0.81			
SL5	Male	132	0.29	0.45	0.47	215	0.642
	Female	85	0.26	0.44			
SL6	Male	132	1.20	0.98	-1.26	215	0.210
	Female	85	1.35	0.59			
SL7	Male	132	1.23	0.82	-1.78	215	0.077
	Female	85	1.42	0.76			
SL8	Male	132	1.39	0.72	2.43	215	0.016
	Female	85	1.15	0.65			
SL9	Male	132	0.88	0.83	-0.97	215	0.336
	Female	85	0.99	0.79			
Overall SL	Male	132	10.58	6.61	-0.74	215	0.458
	Female	85	11.24	5.80			

Table 6 above shows the independent t-test result of the comparison between male and female in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy. The table reveals that in each of SL1, SL2, SL4, SL5, SL6, SL7, and SL9, the significance (p-value) is greater than 0.05 which means there is no significant difference between male and female in-service teachers' scientific literacy at those levels. In SL3 and SL8, the significance value was lower than 0.05; this means there is a significant difference between male and female in-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy at those levels. In overall measure of scientific literacy difference by gender, a t value of -0.74 was obtained and the degree of freedom is 215. The significance value is 0.458 which is greater than the benchmark 0.05. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers. Consequently, null hypothesis 3 is not rejected but accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study revealed that the scientific literacy of in-service chemistry teachers is higher than that of pre-service chemistry teachers across all the 9 levels of scientific literacy. The t-test analysis showed that the difference is statistically significant in favour of in-service chemistry

teachers across the first 7 levels of scientific literacy (SL1 to SL7); however, the difference was not significant for SL8 and SL9. Overall, it was observed that there is a statistically significant difference in the scientific literacy of pre-service and in-service teachers in favour of in-service chemistry teachers. This finding could be attributed to the difference in classroom experience between pre-service and in-service chemistry teachers in Taraba State. The difference in classroom experience implies that in-service chemistry teachers could have superior ability to connect scientific theoretical knowledge with practical applications as it should be in the teaching and learning process. In contrast, pre-service teachers, still in training, often lack this practical experience and exposure, limiting their ability to contextualize and apply scientific knowledge effectively. Additionally, in-service teachers' familiarity with curriculum demands and student interactions strengthens their pedagogical content knowledge, contributing to their superior scientific literacy.

The finding that in-service chemistry teachers have high scientific literacy agrees with Najah et al. (2023) who observed that professionally trained chemistry teachers exhibited higher knowledge of teaching and assessment in chemistry than the untrained chemistry teachers. The lower observation for scientific literacy of pre-service teachers agrees with Sarini et al. (2024) who found that literacy achievement of prospective science teachers is very low with respect to scientific literacy. In the same vein, it is consistent with Irwanto et al. (2018) who reported that pre-service chemistry teachers' critical thinking skills are at low level. This further proves that the difference in experience contributed to the in-service teachers having higher scientific literacy than pre-service chemistry teachers. Contrastingly, Obodo et al. (2024) reported high scientific literacy of pre-service teachers in ESUT. The possession of high scientific literacy among pre-service teachers may be attributed to the quality of training received from the teacher-training institution they are enrolled in. When provided with relevant and adequate training, pre-service chemistry teachers could acquire science process skills higher than in-service teachers especially due to the fact that the teacher training programme curriculum has changed to meet modern day realities as opposed to the curriculum used to train teachers in 20 to 30 years ago. Clores and Reganit (2020) observed that in-service teachers have medium level literacy in assessment as opposed to high level reported in aforementioned studies. The reported medium level of literacy in assessment which is a component of scientific literacy means that despite the experience, there could be little opportunity provided for in-service teachers to upgrade their content knowledge through professional development. Provision of this service is essential towards improving scientific literacy among in-service chemistry teachers.

It was found that female pre-service teachers have slightly higher scientific literacy than their male counterparts. Female pre-service chemistry teachers scored higher than their male counterparts in SL1, SL2, SL3, SL5, and SL9 while male pre-service chemistry teachers outperformed their female counterparts in SL4, SL6, SL7 and SL8. Notwithstanding, the difference in male and female pre-service chemistry teachers' competencies in scientific literacy was found not to be statistically significant in each of the 9 levels of scientific literacy and the overall scientific literacy. It could be explained from this observation that the chemistry teacher training programmes in the tertiary institutions in Taraba State provide equal access to curriculum content and resources for both male and female students. Both male and female chemistry teacher trainees likely undergo similar coursework and practical exercises, ensuring comparable and identical exposure to scientific concepts. This corroborates Cavas (2015) who reported that pre-service teachers' level of scientific literacy is regardless of their gender. It also agrees with Agbenyeku and Arowolo (2024) who observed no significant difference in the scores of male and female colleges of education science students with reference to scientific literacy. This observation could further be attributed to the fact that societal shifts toward gender equality in education minimize gender disparities in academic preparation. However, variations in individual aptitude or teaching exposure might still exist but not be pronounced enough to create a significant gap as observed in this study's findings. However, the finding disagrees with Kristiyasari et al. (2018) who found that university students' literacy skills are influenced by gender differences. Furthermore, it does not align with the finding of Aina et al. (2020) that showed male college of education students possessed more scientific literacy skills than their female counterparts. The observed gender differences in the studies show that there is no homogeneity of instructions or a particular gender receives more attention over the other. This is opposing the Sustainable Development Goal of attaining gender balance by 2030.

It was also found that female in-service chemistry teachers have higher scientific literacy than their male counterparts. The female in-service chemistry teachers showed higher literacy than their male counterparts in SL2, SL3, SL4, SL6, SL7, and SL9; this means that the female teachers are better than the male teachers in terms of conducting an effective literature search; evaluating the use and misuse of scientific information; understanding elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions; solving problems using quantitative skills; including probability and statistics; and justifying inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data respectively. Male in-service chemistry teachers outperformed their female counterparts in SL1, SL5 and SL8; this means that the male in-service have higher scientific literacy in terms of identifying a valid scientific argument, making a graph and Understand and interpret basic statistics respectively.

However, there was no significant difference in male and female in-service teacher's scientific literacy except for SL3 and SL8 which showed significant differences in favour of female and male in-service teachers respectively. Overall, there was no significant difference in the mean scientific literacy score of male and female in-service chemistry teachers. This could stem from equitable professional development opportunities and standardized teaching certifications that ensure both genders acquire similar levels of scientific knowledge and pedagogical skills. Both male and female teachers likely have comparable classroom experiences, which enhances their ability to apply scientific concepts effectively, regardless of gender. Additionally, curriculum requirements and in-service training programmes in Taraba State are likely designed to cater for gender differences, thereby fostering consistent scientific literacy outcomes irrespective of gender. This finding agrees with Akili and Kuturu (2022) that there is no significant gender difference in scientific literacy of teachers. It also aligns with Malabo (2024) who found that assessment literacy levels did not significantly differ by gender of basic education teachers. Alternatively, the finding is in disagreement with Ihenetu-Hyginus and Wali (2022) who reported that female teachers' assessment literacy level is significantly higher than the male teachers. Environment that believe male chemistry teachers are superior to female chemistry teachers or female teachers being superior to male teachers are responsible for gender disparity in in-service chemistry teachers difference in scientific literacy. Since the scientific literacy of in-service teachers depend on opportunities for professional development and classroom teaching experience, achieving no gender difference spells that both genders get equal opportunities in these regards.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the current teachers of chemistry in Taraba State are better than the potential teachers of chemistry in the domains of scientific literacy. The study also concludes that male and female pre-service teachers show no gender difference in scientific literacy. This means both male and female potential chemistry teachers are being trained and could equally teach chemistry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's findings have made it necessary to recommend that;

1. Pre-service chemistry teachers curriculum and training process should be reviewed. Contents and instructional and training strategies that will foster scientific literacy acquisition should be incorporated into the educational process.
2. The admission and training process of pre-service teachers should continue to take cognisance of the gender difference of the pre-service chemistry teachers.
3. Male and female chemistry teachers should be provided with equal opportunities for professional training in order to boost their scientific literacy

REFERENCES

- Agbenyeku, P. & Arowolo, J. G. (2024). Learning strategies and integrated science students scientific literacy level in colleges of education, North-Central, Nigeria. *Journal of Capital Development in Behavioural Sciences*, 12(1), 1-18.
- Aina, J. K., Abdulrahman, A., O., Ayodele, M. O. (2020). Assessment of scientific literacy skills of college of education students in Nigeria. *American Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(1), 207-220.

- Akili, M. & Kuturu, K. (2022). Determination of scientific literacy levels of primary school teachers and investigation in terms of different variables. *Kastamonu Eğitim Dergisi*, 30(4), 1-7.
- Budiman, I., Kaniawati, I., Permanasari, A., & Lukmana, I. (2021). Teachers' perspective on scientific literacy in science learning: descriptive survey. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IIPA 7(Special Issue)*, 218–224.
- Cavas, P. H., Ozdem, Y., Cavas, B., Cakiroglu, J., & Ertepinar, H. (2015). Turkish pre-service elementary science teachers' scientific literacy level and attitudes toward science. *Science Education International*, 24(4), 383-401.
- Clores, M. A. & Reganit, A. A. R. (2020). Investigating the assessment literacy of teachers in private junior high schools in the Philippines. *Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Studies*, 20(2), 461-476
- Ezeh, D. N. (2016). Influence of gender and location on students' achievement in chemical bonding. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(3), 309-318.
- Fred, F. & Femi, B. (2024). Investigating the scientific literacy and process skills of pre-service and in-service science teachers. *International Journal of Studies in Education*, 20(3), 314-321.
- Gambari, A. I., Obielodan, O. O. & Kawu, H (2017). Effects of virtual laboratory on achievement levels and gender of secondary school chemistry students in individualized and collaborative settings in Minna, Nigeria. *The Online Journal of New Horizons in Education*, 7(1), 86-102.
- Gormally, C., Brickman, P. & Lutz, M. (2012). Developing a test of scientific literacy skills (TOSLS): Measuring undergraduates' evaluation of scientific information and arguments. *CBE-Life Sciences Education*, 11(4), 364-377.
- Ihenetu-Hyginus, R. C. & Wali, F. N. (2022). Examining the assessment literacy of the teachers in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *Journal of Education and Society*, 12(3), 2905–2913.
- Irwanto, I., Rohaeti, E. & Prodjosantoso, A. K. (2018). Undergraduate students' science process skills in terms of some variables: A perspective from Indonesia. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 17(5), 751-764.
- Jack, G. U. (2020). Gender difference among science education pre-service teachers' enrolment and achievement in Taraba state, Nigeria. *Journal of Science Technology and Education*, Faculty of Technology Education, ATBU, Bauchi, 8 (1), 277-285.
- Jack, G. U. (2021). Availability, adequacy and effective utilization of ICT resources by practicing pre-service science teachers in Jalingo Metropolis, Taraba State, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 9, 57-66.
- Jack, G. U. & Ayuba, M. (2021). Science teachers' perceptions on availability and utilization of ICT resources in secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Management and Entrepreneurial Studies (AJEMATES)*, 3: 73-88.
- Jack, G. U. & Barau, P. (2021). Assessment of science teachers' competency on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Taraba State. *Journal of Engineering, Computational & Applied Sciences (JECAS)*. Special Issue, 1 (1), 43-54.
- Kristiyasari, M. L., Yamtinah, S., Utomo, S. B., Ashadi, A. & Indriyanti, N. Y. (2018). Gender differences in students' science literacy towards learning on integrated science subject. *IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1097 (2018), 12-20.
- Lemmon, C., Mikell, M. & Cena, C. (2023, November 21). Scientific literacy | definition, importance & examples. Study.com. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/scientific-literacy-definition-examples.html>
- Najah, A. N., Abukari, M. A., Tindan, T. N., Agyei, p., Gonyalug, I. Z. & Mensah, J. D. (2023). Chemistry teachers' knowledge of teaching and assessment of senior high school students. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 6(3), 71-84.
- Obodo, E. C., Izekor, E. S. & Ozoze, P. C. (2024). Investigating the scientific literacy of pre-service science teachers in Enugu State University of science and technology, Enugu State. *International Journal of Studies in Education*, 20(3), 314-321.
- Owusu-Ansah, J. (2017). Assessment of pre-service teachers' competence in the teaching of science in basic schools in Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(4), 17-24.
- Rubini, B., Pustisari, I. D., Ardianto, D. & Hidayat, A. (2018). Science teachers' understanding on science literacy and integrated science learning: lesson from teachers training. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 7(3), 259-265.
- Sarini, P., Widodo, W., Sutoyo, S. & Suardana, N. (2024). Scientific literacy profile of prospective science teacher students. *International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 5(4), 1026-1039.

Test of Scientific Literacy (TOSL) Table of Specifications

LEVEL	DESCRIPTION	ITEM
SL1	Identify a valid scientific argument (e.g., recognizing when scientific evidence supports a hypothesis)	3 (1, 8, 11)
SL2	Conduct an effective literature search (e.g. Evaluate the validity of sources (e.g., websites, peer reviewed journals) and distinguish between types of sources)	5 (10, 12, 17, 22, 26)
SL3	Evaluate the use and misuse of scientific information (e.g Recognize a valid scientific course of action, distinguish the appropriate use of science to make societal decisions)	3 (5, 9, 27)
SL4	Understand elements of research design and how they impact scientific findings/conclusions (e.g. identify strengths and weaknesses in research related to bias, sample size, randomization, experimental control)	4 (4, 13, 14, 25)
SL5	Make a graph i.e. graphical representations of data	1 (15)
SL6	Read and interpret graphical representations of data	4 (2, 6, 7, 18)
SL7	Solve problems using quantitative skills, including probability and statistics (e.g. calculate means, probabilities, percentages, frequencies)	3 (16, 20, 23)
SL8	Understand and interpret basic statistics (e.g. interpret error bars, understand the need for statistics)	3 (3, 19, 24)
SL9	Justify inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data	2 (21, 28)
	TOTAL	28